

8T – Arbitrary Variations Transfer

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T, author will argue that the main equation in universe packet variation is indicating that matter can be transferred across distinct manifolds. that is because the matter cluster being transferred does not interfere with the condition of stationarity.

Introduction

The 8T is a the theory of variational curvature, the main equation (1) is describing the principle of equivalence between gravity and acceleration, and by demanding the two conditions $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$ we have the conditions to "dark energy" which Is the result of distinct manifolds interacting in areas of extremum curvatures, leading to an acceleration from those areas, and

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.42) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

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We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term of equation (1) and derived the existence of Fermions. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

Suppose that we have a finite number of pairs of distinct universes flattening each other via areas of extremum curvatures.

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_m - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_n = 0 \quad (2.1.B)$$

$$K = 2000$$

Let the arbitrary variation terms, we also have a finite number of arbitrary variation vanishing into matter. Notice that if we change the amount in one universe and insert it to another universe, the stationarity condition will hold.

$$\delta g_m \rightarrow \delta g_{\tilde{m}}$$

$$\delta g_n \rightarrow \delta g_{\tilde{n}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\delta g_m &< \delta g_{\tilde{m}} \\ \delta g_{\tilde{n}} &> \delta g_n \\ \delta g_m - \delta g_{\tilde{m}} &= \Delta \\ \delta g_{\tilde{n}} - \delta g_n &= \Delta\end{aligned}$$

In other words, the term Δ is the amount of arbitrary variations that vanished into matter, and transferred from the first manifold into the second manifold. The only requirement is that that this amount would be an even amount of variations that will ensure that the manifold will stay at the condition of stationarity.

$$\begin{aligned}2|\Delta &\rightarrow True \\ \sum_{m=1}^{\frac{K}{2}-\Delta} \delta g_m &< \sum_{n=1}^{\frac{K}{2}+\Delta} \delta g_n \\ \sum_{m=1}^{\frac{K}{2}-\Delta} \delta g_m = 0 &\cap \sum_{n=1}^{\frac{K}{2}+\Delta} \delta g_n = 0\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, despite matter can jump across the manifolds while keeping the manifold stationary, there is still a conservation of variation if we consider that matter can not escape the packet. Such idea is than revolutionary as it is imply it is impossible to know whether matter was originally created from variations of our own manifold, or it is matter which "jumped" or was transferred from a distinct manifold. That means that within one universe the conservation of energy does not hold, as matter has a potential energy, i.e. curvature in the 8T framework as was previously covered in the thesis. That idea however shades light on a conservation law, which indicates that while matter can jump from manifold to manifold, it can not escape the packet itself. So there is a conservation of entities within the packet. That does not indicate that there is a conservation of energy, as new entities are constantly being created as the manifold has arbitrary variations, all it indicates is the following: once those entities are created they must appear in some manifold within the packet. Nature does not impose a restriction on the index of the manifold that those entities should exist on.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

Manor Ohad